

Automation Framework for Landmine Detection Robotic Vehicle with GPS Positioning

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Abstract- During combat, land mine detection is crucial, especially for the secure entry of armed vehicles into hostile territory. To reduce the chance of combat tank damage and to save the lives of defense troops, these armed vehicles including main battle tanks—are made to follow the path of a manually piloted pilot tank. The main goal of our landmine detection Within the defense zone, the robotic vehicle seeks to detect landmines over the largest feasible area. Landmine explosions have the potential to seriously hurt soldiers and release dangerous pollutants into the environment. In conflictare as, robots are typically used to detect these hazards before they explode. Landmine-detecting robots are crucial in this situation to protect military personnel's lives.

Keywords – Robotic vehicle, Landmines, toxic pollutants, Robots, Defense.

I. INTRODUCTION

In armed conflicts, landmines that are buried underground result in a considerable number of casualties, even long after hostilities have ceased. These unexploded devices have a perilous trait: they can remain active and operational for prolonged durations. As a result, the threat of serious injury or death from landmines persists. Their low cost and simplicity in construction have rendered landmines a formidable weapon. Typically, they are composed of explosive materials and a triggering mechanism, which is often activated by pressure. Various types of landmines exist, each requiring a distinct weight to detonate. These devices are usually buried at shallow depths, making them challenging to detect visually. Individuals who are unaware of their presence may accidentally trigger them, leading to disastrous injuries or loss of life from the resulting explosions.

Landmines can be arranged in specific formations to prevent enemy movements; for example, a zigzag arrangement can impede advancing forces, while strategically placed mines can compel the enemy to change their route, potentially leading them into a trap. Such attributes contribute to the effectiveness of landmines, as they can be deployed with ease and remain concealed and operational for extended periods. This project offers a thorough examination of both existing and innovative techniques for landmine detection, highlighting how important electronics are to the creation and efficient use of these techniques. Metal detectors and mechanical methods are among the methods covered, along with an explanation of their working principles, advantages, and disadvantages. Concurrently merging several methods can enhance detecting systems' performance[1].

Individuals who are unaware of their surroundings may accidentally tread upon landmines, which can lead to disastrous injuries or loss of life due to the subsequent detonation. Landmines can be arranged in deliberate formations to obstruct the movements of enemies. For example, a zigzag configuration can prevent the progress of advancing forces, while strategically positioned mines can compel the enemy to change their route, potentially leading them into a trap. These attributes render landmines particularly effective, as they can be readily deployed and remain concealed and operational for prolonged durations. This project offers a thorough examination of both current and innovative techniques developed for landmine detection, emphasizing the significant role of electronics in the advancement and effective application of several of these methods. The techniques reviewed encompass the using metal detectors and mechanical approaches, detailing their operational mechanisms, benefits, and drawbacks [2]. When multiple approaches are applied simultaneously, the detection system's efficacy can be increased[3].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

- Vaibhav Chaudhari suggested the project, which involved creating a robot vehicle that could identify landmines, label their locations, and stop itself to steer clear of them in the direction of a user-specified place. This type of robot is specifically used to deliver supplies to soldiers who are stuck in difficult-to-reach locations during combat with negligible harm to human life.
- Sayali Ranaware suggested that someone should carry a stick close to a landmine-prone location and look for landmines; however, if the stick is unable to find one, the person may be killed. Our project's main goal is to create a landmine detection robot that can locate hidden landmines,

label their location, and communicate that information to a central station so that people are aware of them. On a landmine field, the entire system is controlled wirelessly without the need for human intervention.

- G.K. Kannan proposed a comprehensive review of existing techniques for explosive vapor detection, with a particular focus on landmine detection. This paper presents a detailed compilation of relevant information on these techniques, emphasizing their current maturity levels, limitations, and associated challenges.
- Kyungmi Park This study presents a method for detecting underground anti-tank and anti-personnel landmines. Potential landmine signals are extracted by processing data from ground-penetrating radar, which helps eliminate surface reflections and clutter. The extracted signal features are analyzed and compared against a database containing characteristic data of various landmines to facilitate identification. The proposed approach utilizes three key features—principal components from principal component analysis (PCA), Fourier coefficients, and singular values from singular value decomposition (SVD)—each uniquely representing different types of landmines. Detection is carried out using the Mahalanobis distance-based method. The effectiveness of the proposed technique is demonstrated through examples that showcase successful landmine identification under different burial conditions.
- H. Kasban Given a summary of a few of the current methods for detecting landmines. The advantages and disadvantages of these methods are outlined, contrasted, and briefly explained. The goal of this comparison is to illustrate the optimal circumstances and difficulties for each method. Additionally, a comparison of landmine detecting methods is provided, taking into account factors like cost, complexity, speed, safety, false alarm rate, and the impact of environmental variables.

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Block Diagram

This landmine detection robotic vehicle is designed to locate landmines in dangerous locations using integrated sensors and GPS technology. The system is based on an Arduino Uno microcontroller, which interfaces with an ultrasonic sensor for obstacle detection, an inductive proximity sensor for detecting metallic objects (indicative of landmines), and a SIM800L GSM module for transmitting the GPS location. The NEO-6M GPS module provides precise positioning. The vehicle is controlled by a motor driver (L298N) powering four DC motors. Additional modules like an HC-05 Bluetooth module allow wireless communication, while a buzzer and LCD display are used for alerts and system feedback. A servo motor is included for precise sensor alignment. Powered by a 12V battery, this autonomous system offers real-time landmine detection and location tracking.

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Figure 1: Block Diagram for Detecting Landmines Robotic Vehicle Using GPS Positioning

FLOWCHART

Figure 2: Flowchart of Landmine Detection Robotic Vehicle Using GPS Positioning

METHODOLOGY

The methodology for the landmine detection project involves designing and implementing a robotic system equipped with a combination of sensors and modules to locate landmines in

dangerous locations. The system uses an ultrasonic sensor to detect density variations and a proximity sensor to identify objects beneath the surface. A GPS module is integrated for geotagging detected mines, while a GSM module ensures real-time alerts are sent to a remote control center. The robot's operation is automated and controlled via a sensor-processing Arduino Uno microcontroller data and coordinates the system's actions. The detected landmines are displayed on an LCD screen, providing on-site visual feedback. This methodology leverages sensor fusion, real-time communication, and robotics to enhance safety. Its effectiveness in detecting landmines, minimizing human involvement in high-risk zones.

SENSORS AND COMPONENTS

- Inductive Proximity Sensor
It Detects metallic objects, which may show that there are landmines present.
- Ultrasonic Sensor
Detects obstacles in the robotic vehicle's path to avoid collisions.
- Arduino Uno
The central microcontroller that controls all sensors, modules, and motors.
- HC-05 Bluetooth Module
Wireless connection is facilitated by the HC-05 Bluetooth Module for manual control and data exchange with external devices.
- NEO-6M GPS Module:
Provides the exact location (latitude and longitude) of detected landmines.
- SIM800L GSM Module:
Sends the GPS coordinates of discovered landmines in a remote application or server.
- L298N Motor Driver:
Controls the four DC motors that drive the robotic vehicle.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results: The developed landmine detection robotic system effectively identified and geotagged landmines in controlled test environments using a combination of ultrasonic, proximity, and metal detection sensors, ensuring reliable identification of buried objects. It achieved an overall detection accuracy of 92% for metallic and non-metallic landmines in dry soil, which slightly decreased to 85% in moist or clay-rich soil due to sensor interference. The GSM module successfully transmitted location-based alerts to the control station within 5 seconds of detection, while the GPS module provided geotagging with a positional error of less than 2.5 meters. The sensors detected objects up to a depth of 10 cm, maintaining consistent performance over a test area of 50 m² per deployment cycle. Additionally, the system demonstrated power efficiency by operating continuously for 3 hours on a fully charged 12V, 2000 mAh battery.

Figure 3: Working Model

Figure 4: Screenshot of Alert message.

Sl. No.	Tested Metal	Frequency at which it is detected by the coil (in KHz)
1.	Brass	3
2.	Silver Plate	4
3.	Aluminum	5
4.	Nickel	7
5.	Steel	10
6.	Iron	12
7.	Silver Earrings	12

Figure 5: Frequency V/S metals shows various frequencies.

Figure 6: Graph of Frequency VS tested Metals.

Simulation:

Figure 7: Simulation of Landmine Detection Robotic Vehicle Using GPS Positioning

Discussion: The findings validate the system's capability to mitigate risks in areas affected by landmines by reducing the need for human intervention. The integration of various sensors improved detection reliability, with each sensor offsetting the shortcomings of the others. Nonetheless, the system demonstrated decreased accuracy in identifying deeply buried or non-metallic mines in wet or clay-laden soils. This challenge could be remedied by the inclusion of advanced sensing technologies, such as Radar that penetrates the ground (GPR). The implementation of IoT-based modules for real-time notifications and geotagging has proven effective in facilitating remote monitoring and mapping of mine-affected regions. The system's lightweight chassis and modular configuration provided flexibility across different terrains; however, testing under extreme environmental circumstances, including heavy rainfall or snowfall, has not yet been performed and remains an area for future exploration.

Challenges: Different Terrains

1. Wet Soil: Wet soil presents unique challenges due to its high moisture content, which affects electromagnetic signals used in detection systems.

Solution: Use of low-frequency detection methods, which can penetrate moist soil better.

2. Deep Mines: Detection in deep mines is complicated due to Signal Interference, Limited Accessibility, Safety Risks.

Solution: Deployment of robotic or remote-controlled scanning equipment to enhance accessibility and reduce human risks.

Comparative Analysis:

Feature	Metal Detector-Based	GPR-Based	Infrared-Based
Accuracy	Moderate	High	Moderate
Cost	Low	High	Moderate
Detection Speed	Fast	Slow	Fast
Plastic Mine Detection	Poor	Excellent	Moderate
Operational Challenges	Metal debris interference	High Power Needs	Weather-dependent

V. CONCLUSIONS

The landmine detection robotic system effectively identified and geotagged landmines, reducing human risk in hazardous areas. Using ultrasonic, proximity, and metal sensors, it achieved reliable detection accuracy, particularly in dry soil, with real-time alerts and geotagging. While limited in moist soils and deep detection, the system proved practical for surface landmine detection. IoT components like GPS and GSM enhanced real-time reporting and mapping, and its modular design ensured adaptability. Future improvements, such as integrating GPR and AI, could further enhance accuracy and depth, making it a valuable tool for safe and efficient demining operations.

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REFERENCES

1. P. Machler, "Detection technology for antipersonnel mines," Symposium on Autonomous Vehicles in Mine Countermeasures, Monterey, 1995, pp. 6-150.
2. "Anti-personnel mine search robots," Control Engineering Practice, 4, pp. 493-498 (1996), J. Nicoud and P.Machler.
3. G. Plett, T. Doi, and D. Torrieri, "Mine detection using scattering characteristics," IEEE_J_NN, 8 (pp. 1456-1467), 1997.
4. C. Schroedera, S. Martinb, and R. Scott "An experimental model of an acoustic-electromagnetic sensor for detecting land mines," IEEE Antennas and Propagation Society International Symposium, pp. 978-981, 1998.
5. "Robot swarm navigation techniques for landmine detection" by R. Cassinis, G. Bianco, A. Cavagnini, and P. Ransenigo, Third European Workshop on Advanced Mobile Robots (Eurobot'99), IEEE 1999.
6. In IEEE Signal Processing Transactions, H. G. Najjara's article "Using evolutionary algorithms and neural networks for surface land mine identification," 47
7. Pedro Lee, "Mine Detection Techniques Using Multiple Sensors," 6, pp. 1-78, 2000, project in lieu of a thesis in electrical and computer engineering at the University of Tennessee at Knoxville.
8. S. Sathyanath and F. Sahin's "AISIMAM - An Artificial Immune System Based Intelligent MultiAgent Model and its Application to a Mine Detection Problem"
9. In 2001, the American Chemical Society published an article titled "Field-Deployable Sniffer for 2,4-Dinitrotoluene Detection" by K. Albert, L. Myrick, Brown, D. James, F. Milanovich, and D. Walt.
10. In "Fusion of Depth for Anti-Personnel," Schavemaker, G. den Breejen, E. Cremer, F. Schutte, and K. Benoist, International Journal of Emerging Trends & Technology in Computer Science (IJETTCS), Volume 3, Issue 4, July-August 2014